

m -POLAR CUBIC SET THEORY APPLIED TO BCK/BCI -ALGEBRAS

G. MUHIUDDIN* AND AHSAN MAHBOOB

ABSTRACT. In this paper, by combining the notions of m -polar fuzzy structures and interval valued m -polar fuzzy structures, the notion of m -polar cubic structures is introduced and applied on the ideal theory of BCK/BCI -algebras. In this respect, the notions of m -polar cubic subalgebras and m -polar cubic (commutative) ideals are introduced and some essential properties are discussed. Characterizations of m -polar cubic subalgebras and m -polar cubic (commutative) ideals are considered. Moreover, the relations among m -polar cubic subalgebras, m -polar cubic ideals and m -polar cubic commutative ideals are obtained.

1. INTRODUCTION

Imai and Iséki presented the BCK/BCI -algebras [13, 14] in 1966, which is an extension of set-theoretic difference and propositional calculus. Since then, a lot of research has emerged on the theory of BCK/BCI -algebras, with a particular focus on the ideal theory of BCK/BCI -algebras. Different types of ideals were examined in various methods in BCK/BCI -algebras (see, for example, [15, 16, 27, 28, 31]).

By combining the notions of fuzzy sets and interval valued fuzzy sets, Jun et al. [21] introduced the notion of cubic sets (see [22, 23, 24] for related ideas and results on cubic ideals in BCK/BCI -algebras). Thereafter, the notion of cubic ideals was introduced in different algebraic structures and studied by several authors, for instance, Muhiuddin et al. [32, 33], Senapati et al. [38, 39, 40], Gaketem et al. [11], Gulistan [12], Yaqoob et al. [42], and many others.

In 2014, Chen et al. [8] presented the m -polar fuzzy set, an expansion of the bipolar fuzzy set. The m -polar fuzzy models provide the framework with more accuracy, versatility and compatibility when more than one variables needs to be taken. The m -polar fuzzy algebraic structures study began with the concept of m - pF lie subalgebras introduced by Akram et al. [1]. After that, the theory of m - pF lie ideals was introduced by Akram et al. [1] in lie subalgebras. A concept given by [10] for the m - pF subgroups. Al-Masarwah et al [3] proposed the concepts of m - pF ideals and m - pF commutative ideals on BCK/BCI -algebras. To make this paper self-readable, readers are suggested to read [6, 34, 35, 36, 37].

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*Corresponding author.

In this paper, by combining the notions of m -polar fuzzy sets and interval valued m -polar fuzzy sets, the notion of m -polar cubic structures is introduced and applied on the ideal theory of BCK/BCI -algebra. In this respect, we introduce the notions of m -polar cubic subalgebra, m -polar cubic ideals and m -polar cubic commutative ideals. We prove that m -polar cubic ideals are m -polar cubic subalgebras but the converse statement is not valid and an example is given in this support. We provide a condition under which m -polar cubic subalgebra becomes an m -polar cubic ideal. Moreover, we prove that m -polar cubic commutative ideals are m -polar cubic ideals but the converse implication is not true and an example is given in this aim. Also, a condition under which m -polar cubic ideal becomes an m -polar cubic commutative ideal is provided.

2. PRELIMINARIES

An algebra $(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}; *, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is said to be a BCI -algebra if:

- (K_1) $((\vartheta * \ell) * (\vartheta * \varrho)) * (\varrho * \ell) = 0,$
- (K_2) $(\vartheta * (\vartheta * \ell)) * \ell = 0,$
- (K_3) $\vartheta * \vartheta = 0,$
- (K_4) $\vartheta * \ell = 0$ and $\ell * \vartheta = 0 \Rightarrow \vartheta = \ell,$
- $\forall \vartheta, \varrho, \ell \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}.$

If a BCI -algebra $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ satisfies the condition:

- (K_5) $0 * \vartheta = 0, \forall \vartheta \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}},$

then $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is a BCK -algebra, .

Any BCK/BCI -algebra $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ has the following properties:

- (π_1) $\vartheta * 0 = \vartheta,$
- (π_2) $(\vartheta * \ell) * \varrho = (\vartheta * \varrho) * \ell,$
- (π_3) $\vartheta \leq \ell \Rightarrow \vartheta * \varrho \leq \ell * \varrho$ and $\varrho * \ell \leq \varrho * \vartheta,$
- (π_4) $0 * (\vartheta * \ell) = (0 * \vartheta) * (0 * \ell),$
- (π_5) $0 * (0 * (\vartheta * \ell)) = 0 * (\ell * \vartheta),$
- (π_6) $(\vartheta * \varrho) * (\ell * \varrho) \leq (\vartheta * \ell),$
- (π_7) $\vartheta * (\vartheta * (\vartheta * \ell)) = \vartheta * \ell,$
- (π_8) $0 * (0 * ((\vartheta * \varrho) * (\ell * \varrho))) = (0 * \ell) * (0 * \vartheta),$
- (π_9) $0 * (0 * (\vartheta * \ell)) = (0 * \ell) * (0 * \vartheta),$

where $\vartheta \leq \ell \Leftrightarrow \vartheta * \ell = 0 \forall \vartheta, \varrho, \ell \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$. Note that $(\tilde{\mathcal{A}}, \leq)$ is a partially ordered set.

A set $Z (\neq \emptyset)$ of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is said to be a *subalgebra* of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ if $\vartheta * \ell \in Z \forall \vartheta, \ell \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and it is called an *ideal* of Z if $0 \in Z$ and $\forall \vartheta, \varrho \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}, \vartheta * \varrho \in Z, \varrho \in Z$ implies $\vartheta \in Z$. Further, Z is called commutative ideal of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ if $0 \in Z$ and $\forall \vartheta, \varrho, \omega \in Z, ((\vartheta * \omega) * (\varrho * \omega)) \in Z, \varrho \in Z$ implies $\vartheta \in Z$.

We mean an interval defined by $[r^-, r^+]$ where $0 \leq r^- \leq r^+ \leq 1$ by an interval number \tilde{r} . $D[0, 1]$ denotes the set of all interval numbers. For the intervals $[r_i^-, r_i^+], [s_i^-, s_i^+] \in D[0, 1], i \in I$, we define

- (a) $\min\{[r_i^-, r_i^+], [s_i^-, s_i^+]\} = [\min(r_i^-, s_i^-), \min(r_i^+, s_i^+)];$
- (b) $\max\{[r_i^-, r_i^+], [s_i^-, s_i^+]\} = [\max(r_i^-, s_i^-), \max(r_i^+, s_i^+)];$
- (c) $[r_i^-, r_i^+] \leq [s_i^-, s_i^+] \Leftrightarrow r_i^- \leq s_i^-$ and $r_i^+ \leq s_i^+;$
- (d) $[r_i^-, r_i^+] = [s_i^-, s_i^+] \Leftrightarrow r_i^- = s_i^-$ and $r_i^+ = s_i^+.$

Assume that $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is a BCK/BCI-algebra. A mapping $\widetilde{\Psi}^P : \tilde{\mathcal{A}} \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ is referred to as an interval valued fuzzy set (IVFS) in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$, where $\widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) = [\widetilde{\Psi}^{P-}(\vartheta), \widetilde{\Psi}^{P+}(\vartheta)] \forall \vartheta \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$, $\widetilde{\Psi}^{P-}$ and $\widetilde{\Psi}^{P+}$ are fuzzy sets of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ with $\widetilde{\Psi}^{P-}(\vartheta) \leq \widetilde{\Psi}^{P+}(\vartheta), \forall \vartheta \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$.

Definition 2.1. A cubic set \mathcal{C}_S on $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is a structure

$$\mathcal{C}_S = \{(\vartheta, \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta), \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta)) \mid \vartheta \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}\}$$

which is denoted by $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$, where $\widetilde{\Psi}^P$ is an IVFS and $\widetilde{\Phi}^P$ is a FS in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$.

Definition 2.2. A mapping $\widetilde{\Phi}^P : \tilde{\mathcal{A}} \rightarrow [0, 1]^m$ is referred to as an m -polar fuzzy set (mpF set) of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and is described as:

$$\widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) = (\widetilde{\varpi}_1 \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta), \widetilde{\varpi}_2 \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta), \dots, \widetilde{\varpi}_m \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta))$$

where $\widetilde{\varpi}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta)$ represents the i -th degree of membership of ϑ .

Define an order “ \leq ” on $[0, 1]^m$ as pointwise i.e.,

$$\vartheta \leq \varrho \Leftrightarrow \widetilde{\varpi}_i(\vartheta) \leq \widetilde{\varpi}_i(\varrho) \forall 1 \leq i \leq m.$$

The i -th projection mapping is represented as $\widetilde{\varpi}_i : [0, 1]^m \rightarrow [0, 1]$. We mean $(\ell, \ell, \dots, \ell)$ by $\widetilde{\ell} \in [0, 1]^m$. Thus, the smallest and greatest elements in $[0, 1]^m$ are $\widetilde{0}$ and $\widetilde{1}$.

Definition 2.3. A mapping $\widetilde{\Psi}^P : \tilde{\mathcal{A}} \rightarrow D[0, 1]^m$ is referred to as an interval valued m -polar fuzzy set ($IVmPF$ set) of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and is described as:

$$\widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) = (\widetilde{\varpi}_1 \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta), \widetilde{\varpi}_2 \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta), \dots, \widetilde{\varpi}_m \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta)),$$

where $\widetilde{\varpi}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P$ represents the i -th degree of membership of ϑ .

That is

$$\widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) = ([\Psi^{P-}_1(\vartheta), \Psi^{P+}_1(\vartheta)], [\Psi^{P-}_2(\vartheta), \Psi^{P+}_2(\vartheta)], \dots, [\Psi^{P-}_m(\vartheta), \Psi^{P+}_m(\vartheta)]), \forall \vartheta \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$$

where Ψ^{P-}_i and Ψ^{P+}_i are fuzzy sets of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ with $\Psi^{P-}_i(\vartheta) \leq \Psi^{P+}_i(\vartheta), \forall \vartheta \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and $1 \leq i \leq m$.

On $D[0, 1]^m$, a pointwise order is defined as follows:

$$\vartheta \leq \varrho \Leftrightarrow \widetilde{\varpi}_i(\vartheta) \leq \widetilde{\varpi}_i(\varrho), \forall 1 \leq i \leq m.$$

The j -th projection mapping is represented as $\widetilde{\varpi}_i : D[0, 1]^m \rightarrow D[0, 1]$. We mean $\{[\Theta, \theta], [\Theta, \theta], \dots, [\Theta, \theta]\}$ when we say $[\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}] \in D[0, 1]^m$. Thus, the smallest and greatest elements in $D[0, 1]^m$ are $[\widetilde{0}, \widetilde{0}]$ and $[\widetilde{1}, \widetilde{1}]$.

3. m-POLAR CUBIC SUBALGEBRAS

mpC subalgebras in BCK/BCI-algebras are described and characterised in this section.

Definition 3.1. Let $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ be a BCK/BCI-algebra. An m -polar cubic set \mathcal{C}_S (briefly, $mpCS$) is a structure

$$\mathcal{C}_S = \{(\vartheta, \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta), \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta)) \mid \vartheta \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}\}$$

which is denoted by $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$, where $\widetilde{\Psi}^P$ is an $IVmPFS$ and $\widetilde{\Phi}^P$ is an $mpFS$ in $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$.

Definition 3.2. An $mpCS$ $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is called an mpC subalgebra (briefly, $mpCSub$) if:

$$(C1) (\forall \vartheta, \varrho \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}) \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \geq \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \wedge \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho),$$

$$(C2) (\forall \vartheta, \varrho \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}) \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \leq \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta) \vee \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\varrho),$$

that is,

$$(C1) (\forall \vartheta, \varrho \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}, 1 \leq \iota \leq m) \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \geq \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\varrho),$$

$$(C2) (\forall \vartheta, \varrho \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}, 1 \leq \iota \leq m) \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \leq \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\varrho).$$

Example 3.3. Consider a *BCK*-algebra $\tilde{\mathcal{A}} = \{0, \vartheta, \varrho, \ell\}$ with the following table.

*	0	ϑ	ϱ	ℓ
0	0	0	0	0
ϑ	ϑ	0	0	ϑ
ϱ	ϱ	ϑ	0	ϱ
ℓ	ℓ	ℓ	ℓ	0

TABLE 1. Cayley table for $*$ -operation

Let $[\widehat{\omega}, \widehat{\varphi}] = ([\omega_1, \varphi_1], [\omega_2, \varphi_2], \dots, [\omega_m, \varphi_m])$, $[\widehat{\Theta}, \widehat{\theta}] = ([\Theta_1, \theta_1], [\Theta_2, \theta_2], \dots, [\Theta_m, \theta_m]) \in D[0, 1]^m$ and $\widehat{j} = (j_1, j_2, \dots, j_m)$, $\widehat{\varepsilon} = (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_m) \in [0, 1]^m$ be such that $[\widehat{\omega}, \widehat{\varphi}] \geq [\widehat{\Theta}, \widehat{\theta}]$ and $\widehat{j} \geq \widehat{\varepsilon}$. Now define an *mpCS* $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi^P}, \widetilde{\Phi^P})$ on $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ as:

*	$\widetilde{\Psi^P}$	$\widetilde{\Phi^P}$
0	$[\widehat{\omega}, \widehat{\varphi}] = ([\omega_1, \varphi_1], [\omega_2, \varphi_2], \dots, [\omega_m, \varphi_m])$	$(0, 0, \dots, 0)$
ϑ	$[\widehat{\Theta}, \widehat{\theta}] = ([\Theta_1, \theta_1], [\Theta_2, \theta_2], \dots, [\Theta_m, \theta_m])$	$(0, 0, \dots, 0)$
ϱ	$([0, 0], [0, 0], \dots, [0, 0])$	$\widehat{\varepsilon} = (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_m)$
ℓ	$([0, 0], [0, 0], \dots, [0, 0])$	$\widehat{j} = (j_1, j_2, \dots, j_m)$

TABLE 2. Table for the membership values

It is straightforward to show that $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi^P}, \widetilde{\Phi^P})$ is a *3pCS* of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$.

Lemma 3.1. *If $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi^P}, \widetilde{\Phi^P})$ is an *mpCS* of $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$, then*

$$\widetilde{\Psi^P}(0) \geq \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta) \text{ and } \widetilde{\Phi^P}(0) \leq \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta) \forall \vartheta \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}.$$

Proof. Let $\vartheta \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(0) &= \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta * \vartheta) \\ &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(0) &= \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta * \vartheta) \\ &\leq \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta), \end{aligned}$$

as required. \square

Definition 3.4. Let $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi^P}, \widetilde{\Phi^P})$ be any *mpCS*. For $[\widehat{\Theta}, \widehat{\theta}] = ([\Theta_1, \theta_1], [\Theta_2, \theta_2], \dots, [\Theta_m, \theta_m]) \in D[0, 1]^m$ and $\widehat{\varepsilon} = (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_m) \in [0, 1]^m$ define a level set $U(\widetilde{\Psi^P}; [\widehat{\Theta}, \widehat{\theta}], \widehat{\varepsilon})$ as follows:

$$U(\widetilde{\Psi^P}; [\widehat{\Theta}, \widehat{\theta}], \widehat{\varepsilon}) = \{x \in \tilde{\mathcal{A}} \mid \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(x) \geq [\Theta_\iota, \theta_\iota] \text{ and } \widetilde{\omega}_\iota \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(x) \leq \varepsilon_\iota \forall 1 \leq \iota \leq m\}.$$

Theorem 3.2. An mpCS $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ is an mpCSub of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}} \Leftrightarrow$ each $(\emptyset \neq)U(\widetilde{\Psi}^P; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \hat{\varepsilon})$ is a subalgebra of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$, $\forall [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}] = ([\Theta_1, \theta_1], [\Theta_2, \theta_2], \dots, [\Theta_m, \theta_m]) \in D[0, 1]^m$ and $\hat{\varepsilon} = (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_m) \in [0, 1]^m$.

Proof. (\Rightarrow) Take any $\vartheta, \varrho \in U(\widetilde{\Psi}^P; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \hat{\varepsilon})$. Therefore $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \geq [\Theta_i, \theta_i]$, $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) \leq \varepsilon_i$ and $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \geq [\Theta_i, \theta_i]$, $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho) \leq \varepsilon_i$. As $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ is an mpCSub of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$, so we have

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \\ &\geq [\Theta_i, \theta_i] \wedge [\Theta_i, \theta_i] \\ &= [\Theta_i, \theta_i] \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) &\leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho) \\ &\leq \varepsilon_i \vee \varepsilon_i \\ &= \varepsilon_i. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\vartheta * \varrho \in U(\widetilde{\Psi}^P; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \hat{\varepsilon})$.

(\Leftarrow) Assume that $U(\widetilde{\Psi}^P; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \hat{\varepsilon})$ is subalgebra of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$, $\forall [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}] = ([\Theta_1, \theta_1], [\Theta_2, \theta_2], \dots, [\Theta_m, \theta_m]) \in D[0, 1]^m$ and $\hat{\varepsilon} = (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_m) \in [0, 1]^m$. On contrary, let $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) < \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho)$ and $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) > \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho)$ for some $\vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. So there exist $[\delta, \gamma] = ([\delta_1, \gamma_1], [\delta_2, \gamma_2], \dots, [\delta_m, \gamma_m]) \in D[0, 1]^m$ and $\hat{\ell} = (\ell_1, \ell_2, \dots, \ell_m) \in [0, 1]^m$ such that $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) < [\delta_i, \gamma_i] \leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho)$ and $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) > \ell_i \geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho)$ for each $1 \leq i \leq m$ implies $\vartheta, \varrho \in U(\widetilde{\Psi}^P; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \hat{\varepsilon})$ but $\vartheta * \varrho \notin U(\widetilde{\Psi}^P; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \hat{\varepsilon})$, which is not possible. Therefore $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho)$ and $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho)$, $\forall \vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and $1 \leq i \leq m$. Hence $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ is an mpCSub of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. \square

4. m-POLAR CUBIC IDEALS

In this section, the concept of mpC ideal in BCK/BCI-algebras is described, and associated properties of mpC ideals and mpC subalgebras are discussed.

Definition 4.1. An mpCS $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ is called an mpC ideal (briefly, mpCI) if:

- (C3) $(\forall \vartheta \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}) \widetilde{\Psi}^P(0) \geq \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta)$ and $\widetilde{\Phi}^P(0) \leq \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta)$,
- (C4) $(\forall \vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}) \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \geq \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho)$,
- (C5) $(\forall \vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}) \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) \leq \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \vee \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho)$,

that is,

- (C3) $(\forall \vartheta \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}, 1 \leq i \leq m) \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(0) \geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta)$ and $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(0) \leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta)$,
- (C4) $(\forall \vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}, 1 \leq i \leq m) \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho)$,
- (C5) $(\forall \vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}, 1 \leq i \leq m) \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho)$.

Example 4.2. Consider a BCI-algebra $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}} = \{0, \vartheta, \varrho, \ell\}$ with the following table.

*	0	1	ϑ	ϱ	ℓ
0	0	0	ϑ	ϱ	ℓ
1	1	0	ϑ	ϱ	ℓ
ϑ	ϑ	ϑ	0	ℓ	ϱ
ϱ	ϱ	ϱ	ℓ	0	ϑ
ℓ	ℓ	ℓ	ϱ	ϑ	0

TABLE 3. Cayley table for *-operation

Now define an $3pC$ set $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ on $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ as:

*	$\widetilde{\Psi}^P$	$\widetilde{\Phi}^P$
0	$([0.6, 0.7], [0.5, 0.8], [0.3, 0.4])$	$(0.3, 0.1, 0.2)$
1	$([0.5, 0.6], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3])$	$(0.3, 0.2, 0.1)$
ϑ	$([0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.2])$	$(0.3, 0.3, 0.2)$
ϱ	$([0.3, 0.4], [0.2, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2])$	$(0.6, 0.4, 0.2)$
ℓ	$([0.2, 0.4], [0.1, 0.2], [0.1, 0.2])$	$(0.6, 0.4, 0.2)$

TABLE 4. Table for the membership values

It is simple to show that $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ is a $3pCI$ of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$.

Lemma 4.1. Let $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ be an $mpCI$ of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and $\vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ such that $\vartheta \leq \varrho$. Then

$$\widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \geq \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \text{ and } \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) \leq \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho).$$

Proof. Let $\vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ such that $\vartheta \leq \varrho$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(0) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho). \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) &\leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(0) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho). \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 4.2. Let $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ be an $mpCI$ of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and $\vartheta, \varrho, \hbar \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ such that $\vartheta * \varrho \leq \hbar$. Then

$$\widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \geq \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\hbar) \text{ and } \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) \leq \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho) \vee \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\hbar).$$

Proof. Let $\vartheta, \varrho, \hbar \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ such that $\vartheta * \varrho \leq \hbar$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \\ &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\hbar) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\hbar) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(0) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\hbar) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\hbar) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) &\leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho) \\ &\leq \{\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\hbar)\} \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\hbar) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(0) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\hbar) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\hbar) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \geq \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\hbar)$ and $\widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) \leq \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho) \vee \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\hbar)$. □

Theorem 4.3. Every mpCI of BCK-algebra $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is an mpCSub of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ be any mpCI and $\vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. As $\vartheta * \varrho \leq \vartheta$ in $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$, so by above Lemma 4.1, $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho)$ and $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) \geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho)$. Therefore, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \\ &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \\ &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) &\leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) \\ &\leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho) \\ &\leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ is an mpCSub of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. □

Remark. Converse of above Theorem is not true in general.

Example 4.3. Consider a BCK-algebra $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}} = \{0, \vartheta, \varrho, \ell\}$ with the following table:

*	0	ϑ	ϱ	ℓ
0	0	0	0	0
ϑ	ϑ	0	ϑ	0
ϱ	ϱ	ϱ	0	0
ℓ	ℓ	ℓ	ℓ	0

TABLE 5. Cayley table for *-operation

Now define an 3pC set $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ on $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ as:

*	$\widetilde{\Psi}^P$	$\widetilde{\Phi}^P$
0	([0.7, 0.8], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.3])	(0.3, 0.1, 0.2)
ϑ	([0.5, 0.6], [0.1, 0.3], [0.1, 0.2])	(0.3, 0.2, 0.3)
ϱ	([0.3, 0.4], [0.1, 0.1], [0.1, 0.1])	(0.3, 0.3, 0.2)
ℓ	([0.6, 0.7], [0.3, 0.4], [0.1, 0.3])	(0.6, 0.4, 0.2)

TABLE 6. Table for the membership values

It is easy to verify that $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi^P}, \widetilde{\Phi^P})$ is a $3pCSub$ of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ but not a $3pCI$ of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ because $[0.6, 0.5] = (\pi_1 \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P})(\vartheta) \not\leq \pi_1 \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta * \ell) \wedge \pi_1 \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\ell) = [0.7, 0.6]$.

Theorem 4.4. *Let $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi^P}, \widetilde{\Phi^P})$ be an $mpCSub$ of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. Then $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi^P}, \widetilde{\Phi^P})$ is an $mpCI \Leftrightarrow \forall \vartheta, \varrho, \hbar \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ such that $\vartheta * \varrho \leq \hbar$ implies $\widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta) \geq \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\hbar)$ and $\widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta) \leq \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\varrho) \vee \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\hbar)$.*

Proof. (\Rightarrow) Follows from Lemma 4.2.

(\Leftarrow) Let $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi^P}, \widetilde{\Phi^P})$ be an $mpCSub$ of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ such that for all $\vartheta, \varrho, \hbar \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$, $\vartheta * \varrho \leq \hbar$ implies $\widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta) \geq \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\hbar)$ and $\widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta) \leq \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\varrho) \vee \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\hbar)$. As $\vartheta * (\vartheta * \varrho) \leq \varrho$, so by hypothesis

$$\widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta) \geq \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\varrho) \text{ and } \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta) \leq \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \vee \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\varrho).$$

Hence $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi^P}, \widetilde{\Phi^P})$ is an $mpCI$ of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. \square

Theorem 4.5. *An $mpCS \mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi^P}, \widetilde{\Phi^P})$ is an $mpCI$ of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}} \Leftrightarrow$ each non-empty level subset $U(\widetilde{\Psi^P}; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \widehat{\varepsilon})$ is an ideal of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$, $\forall [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}] = ([\Theta_1, \theta_1], [\Theta_2, \theta_2], \dots, [\Theta_m, \theta_m]) \in D[0, 1]^m$ and $\widehat{\varepsilon} = (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_m) \in [0, 1]^m$.*

Proof. (\Rightarrow) Suppose that $\vartheta * \varrho, \varrho \in U(\widetilde{\Psi^P}; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \widehat{\varepsilon})$. Then $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \geq [\Theta_i, \theta_i]$, $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \leq \varepsilon_i$ and $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\varrho) \geq [\Theta_i, \theta_i]$, $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\varrho) \leq \varepsilon_i \forall 1 \leq i \leq m$. Since $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi^P}, \widetilde{\Phi^P})$ is an $mpCI$ of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$, so we have

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta) &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\varrho) \\ &\geq [\Theta_i, \theta_i] \wedge [\Theta_i, \theta_i] \\ &= [\Theta_i, \theta_i] \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta) &\leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\varrho) \\ &\leq \varepsilon_i \vee \varepsilon_i \\ &= \varepsilon_i. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\vartheta \in U(\widetilde{\Psi^P}; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \widehat{\varepsilon})$.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that $U(\widetilde{\Psi^P}; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \widehat{\varepsilon})$ is ideal of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$, $\forall [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}] = ([\Theta_1, \theta_1], [\Theta_2, \theta_2], \dots, [\Theta_m, \theta_m]) \in D[0, 1]^m$ and $\widehat{\varepsilon} = (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_m) \in [0, 1]^m$. If $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(0) < \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta)$ and $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(0) > \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta)$ for some $\vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. Choose $[\delta, \widehat{\Phi^P}] = ([\delta_1, \gamma_1], [\delta_2, \gamma_2], \dots, [\delta_m, \gamma_m]) \in D[0, 1]^m$ and $\widehat{\ell} = (\ell_1, \ell_2, \dots, \ell_m) \in [0, 1]^m$ such that $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(0) < [\delta_i, \gamma_i] \leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta)$ and $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(0) > \ell_i \geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta)$ for each $1 \leq i \leq m$ implies $\vartheta \in U(\widetilde{\Psi^P}; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \widehat{\varepsilon})$ but $0 \notin U(\widetilde{\Psi^P}; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \widehat{\varepsilon})$, a contradiction. So $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(0) \geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta)$ and $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(0) \leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta) \forall \vartheta \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and $1 \leq i \leq m$. Again, if $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta) < \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\varrho)$ and $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta) > \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\varrho)$ for some $\vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. Choose $[\delta, \widehat{\Phi^P}] = ([\delta_1, \gamma_1], [\delta_2, \gamma_2], \dots, [\delta_m, \gamma_m]) \in D[0, 1]^m$ and $\widehat{\ell} = (\ell_1, \ell_2, \dots, \ell_m) \in [0, 1]^m$ such that $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta) < [\delta_i, \gamma_i] \leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\varrho)$ and $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta) > \ell_i \geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\varrho)$ for each $1 \leq i \leq m$ implies $\vartheta * \varrho \in U(\widetilde{\Psi^P}; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \widehat{\varepsilon})$ and $\varrho \in U(\widetilde{\Psi^P}; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \widehat{\varepsilon})$ but $\vartheta \notin U(\widetilde{\Psi^P}; [\widetilde{\Theta}, \widetilde{\theta}], \widehat{\varepsilon})$, which is a contradiction. So $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta) \geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\vartheta * \varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi^P}(\varrho)$ and $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi^P}(\vartheta) \leq$

$\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho) \forall \vartheta, \varrho \in S$ and $1 \leq i \leq m$. Hence $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ is an *mpCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ \square

5. m-POLAR CUBIC COMMUTATIVE IDEALS

The notion of *mpC* commutative ideal of *BCK/BCI*-algebras is defined in this section. Some connections between *mpC* subalgebras, *mpC* ideals, and *mpC* commutative ideals are studied.

Definition 5.1. An *mpCS* $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is called an *mpC* commutative ideal (briefly, *mpCCI*) if it satisfies (C3) and the following conditions:

- (C6) $(\forall \vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}) \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) \geq \widetilde{\Psi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \wedge \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\hbar),$
- (C7) $(\forall \vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}) \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) \leq \widetilde{\Phi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \vee \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\hbar),$

that is,

- (C6) $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) \geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\hbar),$
- (C7) $\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) \leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\hbar),$

$\forall \vartheta, \varrho, \hbar \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and $1 \leq i \leq m$.

Example 5.2. Consider a *BCK*-algebra $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ of Example 3.3. Let $[\omega_j, \varphi_j], [\Theta_j, \theta_j], [\delta_j, \gamma_j] \in D[0, 1]^m$ be such that $[\omega_j, \varphi_j] \geq [\Theta_j, \theta_j] \geq [\delta_j, \gamma_j] \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$. Now define an *mpCS* $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ on $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ as:

*	$\widetilde{\Psi}^P$	$\widetilde{\Phi}^P$
0	$([\omega_1, \varphi_1], [\omega_2, \varphi_2], \dots, [\omega_m, \varphi_m])$	$(0.3, 0.3, \dots, 0.3)$
ϑ	$([\Theta_1, \theta_1], [\Theta_2, \theta_2], \dots, [\Theta_m, \theta_m])$	$(0.3, 0.3, \dots, 0.3)$
ϱ	$([\delta_1, \gamma_1], [\delta_2, \gamma_2], \dots, [\delta_m, \gamma_m])$	$(0.3, 0.3, \dots, 0.3)$
ℓ	$([\delta_1, \gamma_1], [\delta_2, \gamma_2], \dots, [\delta_m, \gamma_m])$	$(0.3.0.3, \dots, 0.3)$

It is straightforward to verify that \mathcal{C}_S is an *mCCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$.

Theorem 5.1. Every *mpCCI* of *BCK*-algebra $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is an *mpCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ be any *mpCCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and $\vartheta, \varrho, \hbar \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta) &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * (0 * (0 * \vartheta))) \\ &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P((\vartheta * 0) * \varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\varrho). \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta) &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * (0 * (0 * \vartheta))) \\ &\leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P((\vartheta * 0) * \varrho) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\varrho). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ is an *mpCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. \square

Corollary 5.2. Every *mpCCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is an *mpCSub* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$.

Remark. In general, converse of Theorem 5.1 does not hold.

Example 5.3. Consider a *BCK*-algebra $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}} = \{0, \vartheta, j, \varrho, \ell\}$ with the following table.

*	0	ϑ	j	ϱ	ℓ
0	0	0	0	0	0
ϑ	ϑ	0	ϑ	0	0
j	j	j	0	0	0
ϱ	ϱ	ϱ	ϱ	0	0
ℓ	ℓ	ℓ	ϱ	j	0

TABLE 7. Caley table for *-opertaion

Let $\widehat{[\varsigma, \delta]} = ([\varsigma_1, \delta_1], [\varsigma_2, \delta_2], \dots, [\varsigma_m, \delta_m])$, $\widehat{[\psi, \phi]} = ([\psi_1, \phi_1], [\psi_2, \phi_2], \dots, [\psi_m, \phi_m])$, $\widehat{[\rho, \sigma]} = ([\rho_1, \sigma_1], [\rho_2, \sigma_2], \dots, [\rho_m, \sigma_m]) \in D[0, 1]^m$ and $\widehat{\Theta} = (\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \dots, \Theta_m)$, $\widehat{\theta} = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_m)$, $\widehat{\gamma} = (\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_m) \in [0, 1]^m$ be such that $\widehat{[\theta, \delta]} \geq \widehat{[\psi, \phi]} \geq \widehat{[\rho, \sigma]}$ and $\widehat{\Theta} \leq \widehat{\theta} \leq \widehat{\gamma}$. Now define an *mpCS* $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ on $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ as:

*	$\widetilde{\Psi}^P$	δ
0	$\widehat{[\varsigma, \delta]} = ([\varsigma_1, \delta_1], [\varsigma_2, \delta_2], \dots, [\varsigma_m, \delta_m])$	$\widehat{\Theta} = (\Theta_1, \Theta_2, \dots, \Theta_m)$
ϑ	$\widehat{[\psi, \phi]} = ([\psi_1, \phi_1], [\psi_2, \phi_2], \dots, [\psi_m, \phi_m])$	$\widehat{\theta} = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_m)$
j	$\widehat{[\rho, \sigma]} = ([\rho_1, \sigma_1], [\rho_2, \sigma_2], \dots, [\rho_m, \sigma_m])$	$\widehat{\gamma} = (\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_m)$
ϱ	$\widehat{[\rho, \sigma]} = ([\rho_1, \sigma_1], [\rho_2, \sigma_2], \dots, [\rho_m, \sigma_m])$	$\widehat{\gamma} = (\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_m)$
ℓ	$\widehat{[\rho, \sigma]} = ([\rho_1, \sigma_1], [\rho_2, \sigma_2], \dots, [\rho_m, \sigma_m])$	$\widehat{\gamma} = (\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_m)$

TABLE 8. Table for membership values

It is easy to verify that $\widetilde{\Psi}^P$ is an *mpCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ but not an *mpCCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ because $[\rho_1, \sigma_1] = (\pi_1 \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P)(j) = (\pi_1 \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P)(j * (\varrho * (\varrho * j))) \not\leq \pi_1 \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P((j * \varrho) * 0) \wedge \pi_1 \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(0) = (\pi_1 \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P)(0) = [\theta_1, \delta_1]$.

Theorem 5.3. Let $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ be an *mpCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. Then $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ is an *mpCCI* $\Leftrightarrow \forall \vartheta, \varrho \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$,

$$\widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) \geq \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \text{ and } \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) \leq \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho).$$

Proof. (\Rightarrow) Let $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ be an *mpCCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. Then $\forall \vartheta, \varrho, \hbar \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$, we have

$$\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) \geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\hbar)$$

and

$$\widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) \leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\hbar)$$

Taking $\hbar = 0$, so

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * 0) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(0) \\ &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) &\leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * 0) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(0) \\ &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \vee \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \\ &= \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho). \end{aligned}$$

(\Leftarrow) Let $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ be an *mpCI* such that $\forall \vartheta, \varrho, \hbar \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ with $\vartheta * \varrho \leq \hbar$ implies $\widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) \geq \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho)$ and $\widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) \geq \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho)$. By assumption, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \\ &\geq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\hbar) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) &\leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * \varrho) \\ &\leq \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \wedge \widetilde{\omega}_i \circ \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\hbar). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ is an *mpCCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. □

Theorem 5.4. *Every mpCI of commutative BCK-algebra $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is an mpCCI.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ be an *mpCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. Then $\forall \vartheta, \varrho, \hbar \in \widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} ((\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) * ((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar)) * \hbar &= ((\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) * \hbar) * ((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \\ &\leq (\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) * (\vartheta * \varrho) \\ &= (\vartheta * (\vartheta * \varrho)) * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta)) \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

It follows that $((\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) * ((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar)) \leq \hbar$. As $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ is an *mpCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$, so by Lemma 4.2, $\widetilde{\Psi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) \geq \widetilde{\Psi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \wedge \widetilde{\Psi}^P(\hbar)$ and $\widetilde{\Phi}^P(\vartheta * (\varrho * (\varrho * \vartheta))) \leq \widetilde{\Phi}^P((\vartheta * \varrho) * \hbar) \vee \widetilde{\Phi}^P(\hbar)$. Hence $\mathcal{C}_S = (\widetilde{\Psi}^P, \widetilde{\Phi}^P)$ is an *mpCCI* of $\widetilde{\mathcal{A}}$. □

6. CONCLUSION

The *mpCS* provides a new structure with more precision, flexibility and compatibility when more than one variable needs to be taken. The notion of *mpCS* is therefore much wider than the notion of cubic sets. It is therefore necessary to apply the *mpCS* to applications. We constructed the ideal theory in *BCK/BCI*-algebras based on *mpC* structures in this study. We developed the ideas of *mpC* subalgebras, *mpC* ideals, and *mpC* commutative ideals. We showed that *mpC* ideals are *mpC* subalgebra, but the converse is not true, as illustrated by an example in this support. We defined a condition under which an *mpC* subalgebra transforms into an *mpC* ideals. In addition, we defined *mpC* ideals in terms of fuzzy ideals and *BCK/BCI*-algebra ideals. Furthermore, we established that *mpC* commutative ideals are *mpC* fuzzy ideals, but the converse is not true, as illustrated by an example. A condition under which the *mpC* ideal becomes a *mpC* commutative ideal is also presented.

The work offers a new platform in this field for future research and related fields. In fact, this study will serve as a basis for further analysis of the *m*-polar cubic structures in related algebraic structures. The notion presented in this work can be further extended to various algebras such as *RO*-algebras, *BL*-algebras, *MTL*-algebras, *UP*-algebras, *MV*-algebras, *EQ*-algebras and lattice implication algebras, etc.

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G. MUHIUDDIN

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, FACULTY OF SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF TABUK, P.O. BOX 741, TABUK 71491, SAUDI ARABIA

Email address: chishtygm@gmail.com

AHSAN MAHBOOB

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, MADANAPALLE INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY & SCIENCE, MADANAPALLE-517325, INDIA

Email address: khanahsan56@gmail.com